

Abstract

Possible extraterrestrial origin of some complexity of terrestrial biota, including strong differences in physical and mental characteristics between individuals of certain species is discussed.

The origin of high diversity on Earth

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1 Intro

Life on Earth is highly diverse. While most complex life may have evolved locally from relatively simple life-forms, I argue that some of it, or some of its characteristics, probably has an extraterrestrial origin, enhancing the local gene pool.

The hypothesis stems from my previous work, mainly the analysis of the Solar System[1].

2 Extraterrestrial origins

A strong bias toward absolutism and abuse of reductionism exists in modern science. Biology is not an exception. Some forms of energy are considered absolutely living beings, some forms are considered absolutely non-living things. And there are some *intermediate* forms of energy, like viruses, for which there is no consensus. Such approach, coupled with absolutism in physics, leads to absurd notions, such as the implication that absolutely living beings evolve from absolutely non-living things [somehow, spontaneously, with increasing complexity], and the notion that planets cannot be living beings simply because they are composed mostly out of inorganic matter, rather than conventional living cells (physical laws are considered absolutely invariant to scale, which, as my works show, is a mistake). Life on the surface of a planet is not considered to be a part of a larger living being, rather life that evolved on a large piece of rock. Another common assumption is that this life must be limited to planet's surface as, again, under common assumption, based on established theories of planetary formation (even though they are flawed, and evidence exists against them), temperatures and pressures in the interior are globally such that nothing could survive.

However, I have shown[1] that everything is completely relative[2], and planetary formation and development in my theories is such that habitable zones are formed and maintained in the mantle.

Nature and mechanics of life's building blocks (cells) are not invariant to scale, and life itself isn't limited to one discontinuity on one planet. What is

inherently limited is the observer, and if such observer associates strong extroversion with living beings it will hardly interpret extremely introverted forms of energy as living beings. The existence of discrete vertical energy levels, for which I have provided evidence in my works, imply that building blocks of life are different between these levels and not only in scale. A living being as large as the planet, thus, will not (and cannot) be a large pile of microscopic living cells. Blood equivalent flowing in its veins will look nothing at all like human blood, etc.

I argue, in my works, that both atoms and planets are very much alive. And they're not simple life-forms either, they're simply extremely introverted. In other words, they live their lives in, what an extrovert would interpret as, their dreams.

Terrestrial planets are effectively large scale brain equivalents, so complex life probably exists in the interior of most planets, it's the surface life that is time-limited. Evolution of surface life is cultivation of [precursor] neural proteins and cells, which upon maturity migrate to different layers of the upper mantle, where time of migration is correlated with major mass extinctions on the surface. The rate of cultivation is different between different planets, on some it lasts less than a billion years.

Venus, Earth and Mars belong to the same class of life, but not the same species, although Venus and Earth may be more closely related. Nevertheless, precursor neuron proteins (complex life-forms) cultivated on the surface on each of these planets shouldn't differ much qualitatively.

Modern humans, or homo.beta, as I refer to them[3], have been cultivated on both, Mars and Venus, with the biggest physical difference being in size of individuals. These had at least one opportunity to visit Earth and they likely did[4] (I find the probability to be equal to the probability that Earth.homo.beta will visit Mars in near future).

It may be even likely that, in the events of adult planetary neurogenesis surface habitability is temporarily restored and homo.beta is regenerated (re-evolved) on planet's surface.

Mars and Venus could be thus periodically producing humans or humanoids on their surfaces (current neurogenesis on Earth is embryonic, not adult).

Therefore, Mars.homo.beta has likely visited Earth before, but Mars.homo.sapiens, judging by UFO reports, is likely still visiting Earth, probably was, and may still be, involved in hybridization of homo species on Earth.

The source of diversity in characteristics of individuals, and to some degree, diversity in species, is probably, in at least some cases, extraterrestrial DNA introduced during these visits. The DNA of 3 different, but sexually compatible (to high degree, there are some issues with Rh- blood, which is likely indigenous to Mars.homo.beta) species has been mixed into Earth.homo.beta, whose characteristics would not be so diversely expressed otherwise.

2.1 Somatotype

A somatotype represents the body structure and metabolism of an individual. There are 3 general somatotypes, but characteristics of multiple types are often present in an individual.

Endomorph/mesomorph fusion is most common, while ectomorphs are rare.

2.1.1 Mesomorph somatotype

I believe this somatotype is indigenous to Earth and best adapted to its surface atmosphere.

2.1.2 Endomorph somatotype

As incubation of individuals of the same species requires specific temperature, a temperature suitable for life on Earth must have been maintained on Venus and Mars too during the development of homo.beta. Evidently, levels of greenhouse gases have been changing with Sun's output to maintain this temperature on Earth.

One can thus expect the same mechanism existed on Venus and Mars. This mechanism implies inverse relationship of atmospheric CO₂ and O₂.

The metabolism of an endomorph is characterized by high oxygen uptake, required for burning of fatty acids.

Venus is closer to Sun and thus didn't require as much CO₂ and other greenhouse gases as Earth to maintain the needed temperature for life. As low CO₂ implies high O₂, the atmosphere of Venus was perfect for endomorphs.

It is thus possible that the endomorph somatotype originated on Venus and was introduced to Earth. However, if Venus.homo.beta went extinct about 640 million years ago[5] (mya), it is unlikely that this species is responsible for this:

- at that time there was no complex life on Earth, let alone mammals,
- if any mammals were introduced at the time, they obviously went extinct fast as they're absent from fossil records, probably due to unsuitable conditions on Earth for such life forms at the time.

Therefore, if endomorphs were introduced from Venus, they were probably introduced by Venus.homo.sapiens or Mars.homo.sapiens sometime during Phanerozoic, although even homo.beta cannot be excluded as it might be cultivated during periodic adult neurogenesis events on planetary surface.

2.1.3 Ectomorph somatotype

The ectomorphs have low fat tissue as such metabolism prefers oxidation of carbohydrates over fatty acids. Ectomorphs thus have the greatest respiratory exchange ratio (RER) and lowest oxygen uptake[6] among individuals of species.

Since this metabolism is adapted to lower oxygen levels, it may have originated on Mars, as its atmosphere, due to larger distance from the Sun, must

have contained higher amounts of CO₂ and lower amounts of O₂ compared to Earth.

This one probably had to be introduced by Mars.homo.sapiens, quite recently, as ectomorphs on Earth are rare compared to endo/meso hybrids.

2.2 Eye colour

Since eye colour is generally not variable between individuals of the same species in wild animals, it may be a feature introduced by Mars.homo.sapiens. Originally, Earth.homo.beta had brown eye colour. Eye colours from brown to green can be explained by variation of melanin amount in the iris. However, in blue eyes, degree of this variation is much smaller, linking all blue-eyed individuals to a single ancestor[7].

This fact, coupled with the fact that blue eyes are blue due to very low melanin amount makes Mars origin likely - low melanin is expected on Mars due to larger distance from the Sun (lower insolation). If blue eyes do not have Martian origin, grey eyes might have, as they have an even lower amount of melanin. Blue eyes have first appeared 6000-10000 years ago about the Black Sea, and grey eyes should be even younger (2000 years?).

All Mars.homo.beta individuals thus probably had dominantly blue and/or grey eye colours, while Venus.homo.beta must have had darker, dominantly brown eyes.

I have previously hypothesized that *human* soul oscillates between different species. If, as hypothesized, a particular soul has significant affinity for particular blood type then it possibly has affinity for particular eye colour and other DNA encoded properties as well, to some extent. This should not be surprising as bodies and souls co-evolve.

People co-evolve with animals too, thus, inter-species soul oscillation should not be surprising either.

With strong differences in DNA and particularly gene expression between species, inter-species soul oscillation might seem counter-intuitive if soul has affinity for particular body DNA.

However, this is solved with vertical [energy] oscillation of the soul and layered memory. While oscillating within the same species, soul is oscillating horizontally - with no large deviation in mass (energy), bodies between incarnations will generally have similar DNA.

Vertical oscillation of the soul is high energy (mass) oscillation and DNA between bodies will be strongly evolutionary separated, although distance will be decreasing over time.

Decrease in distance (increase in shared DNA) between species over time could then be interpreted as evidence of inter-species soul oscillation.

2.3 Blood types

I have hypothesized previously that Rh negative blood type has extraterrestrial origin. It likely originates on Mars, as Venus and Earth should be more compatible species. This may be true for some other types or factors as well.

2.4 Personality

Judged by somatotype, pure endomorphs are concerned with security, not caring much about freedom. In ectomorphs it is the opposite, while genuine Earthlings seek balance in both.

The current state on Earth and representation of specific somatotypes confirms the hypothesis. All countries have governments providing security (even if more or less imaginary and cancerously - unequally) while true anarchies are non-existent. It is thus the ectomorphs, or Martian characteristics, which are mostly discriminated in society and with a strongest sense of non-belonging.

2.5 Size difference

Over the course of evolution, there have been different species of animals (eg. sharks) in which the most pronounced difference between them is in size.

I do not consider it likely that the same species would evolve twice on Earth at different time and only differ in size, thus, as I have previously hypothesized on the origin of Megalodon and Great White sharks, difference in size may come from difference in size of planets of origin.

2.6 Brain dominance

I have hypothesized elsewhere that progressively evolving life is converging to species in the form of planets, losing limbs and keeping the brain for introverted consciousness.

There are species on Earth already that seem to be far ahead of humans in such evolution. One example are the cephalopods (eg. common octopus), which, effectively, are brains that extend into tentacles. Interestingly, others have already hypothesized that these species have extraterrestrial origin[8], based on other characteristics.

3 Conclusion

I am convinced there is complex life in every planet, every dwarf planet and every moon having a distinct gravitational maximum (soul) - generally, these are bodies in hydrostatic equilibrium.

There should be microscopic life even on some comets and asteroids, hitching a ride in state of hibernation.

Since homo.sapiens likely has means to travel long distances in the Solar System, species on Earth might have been introduced from many of these places, not only Venus and Mars. Exploration of these worlds can confirm this.

As many experiences of homo.sapiens (alien) abduction and stories of non-sexual impregnation (eg. Mary with Jesus, in Christianity) suggest, diversity in characteristics is most likely the result of hybridization by introduction of artificially synthesized foreign gametes into local bodies.

In any case, diversity of species and diversity in characteristics of individuals on one place is implied with life being everywhere and everlasting transformations and changes in soul (energy) momenta (radiation of life should be understood literally as radiation of photons of certain scale).

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